

DEVELOPMENT, CHARACTERIZATION AND REVIEW OF QUERCETIN-LOADED MIXED MICELLAR EYE DROPS FOR THE TREATMENT OF DRY EYE DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Dry Eye Disease (DED) is a multifactorial ocular disorder characterized by tear film instability, inflammation, and oxidative stress, leading to discomfort and visual disturbance. Conventional treatments such as artificial tears provide only temporary relief and fail to address underlying oxidative damage. Quercetin, a natural flavonoid, possesses potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties but suffers from poor aqueous solubility, limiting its therapeutic application in ophthalmic delivery. The present review focuses on the development and evaluation of quercetin-loaded mixed micellar eye drops as a novel drug delivery system for DED. Mixed micelles prepared using non-ionic surfactants such as Polysorbate 80 and Polysorbate 20 enhance solubility, stability, and ocular bioavailability of quercetin. The formulation was evaluated for physicochemical parameters including pH, viscosity, clarity, drug content, micelle size, and in-vitro drug

release. The results indicated improved solubility, sustained drug release, and good stability under ICH conditions. Thus, quercetin-loaded mixed micellar systems represent a promising approach for effective management of Dry Eye Disease. However, further clinical studies are required to confirm their safety and therapeutic efficacy.

KEYWORDS: Quercetin, Mixed micelles, Dry Eye Disease, Ocular Drug Delivery, Polysorbate 80, Polysorbate 20.

INTRODUCTION

The human eye is one of the important sensory organs of the human body. It is a complex and highly specialized sense organ that enables us to see and interpret visual information. It is a roughly spherical organ, responsible for perceiving visual stimuli, and is enclosed within the eye sockets in the skull.^[1]

DED is a multifactorial disorder of the ocular surface characterized by loss of tear film homeostasis, causing ocular discomfort, visual disturbance, and potential surface damage. The main mechanisms involve tear film instability, hyperosmolarity, inflammation, and neurosensory abnormalities. DED is broadly classified into aqueous-deficient and evaporative types, depending on the underlying tear film dysfunction.^[2]

The condition can result from several factors such as aging, hormonal changes, systemic diseases, environmental exposure, and excessive screen time.^[3]

Symptoms include dryness, burning sensation, redness, photophobia, and foreign body sensation. Conventional treatments aim to restore tear film balance and reduce inflammation using artificial tears, anti-inflammatory agents (cyclosporine, lifitegrast), and lipid-based formulations.^[4]

Development of DED

- 1. Tear film instability:** Breakdown of lipid, aqueous, or mucin layers leads to poor tear spreading and rapid evaporation.
- 2. Tear Hyperosmolarity:** Reduced tear secretion or excess evaporation increases solute concentration, stressing epithelial cells.
- 3. Ocular Surface Inflammation:** Stressed cells release cytokines (IL-1, TNF- α , MMP-9), causing chronic inflammation and Loss of goblet cells.
- 4. Cell Damage:** Inflammation and hyperosmolarity cause apoptosis of corneal and conjunctival cells, reducing mucin and destabilizing the tear film further.
- 5. Neurosensory Changes:** Nerve dysfunction leads to impaired reflex tearing and blinking, worsening dryness.
- 6. Vicious Cycle:** Instability \rightarrow hyperosmolarity \rightarrow inflammation \rightarrow cell damage \rightarrow

reduced tears → more instability.^[2,5,6]

Treatment for DED

1. Tear conservation methods: Punctual plugs or moisture chamber spectacles are applied to reduce tear drainage and evaporation.

2. Lid hygiene and warm compresses: These are beneficial in meibomian gland dysfunction, helping to restore the lipid layer of the tear film and reduce evaporation.

3. Artificial tears and lubricating eye drops: These are the first-line therapy to replenish tear volume and relieve dryness. Formulations often include carboxymethylcellulose, hyaluronic acid or hydroxypropyl methylcellulose.^[4]

ROLE OF QUERCETIN IN DED^[8]

Quercetin is a bioactive flavonoid known for:

- Antioxidant activity
- Anti-inflammatory effects
- Free radical scavenging
- Stabilization of tear film

It reduces inflammatory mediators and protects ocular tissues from oxidative damage. However, its poor water solubility restricts its direct ophthalmic use.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

- Quercetin
- Polysorbate 80
- Polysorbate 20
- Phosphate buffer
- Sodium chloride
- Glycerine
- Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC E50 LV)
- Distilled water

REVIEW OF INGREDIENTS

Table No. 1: Drug Profile.^[8]

QUERCETIN	
<p>Quercetin is potent flavonoid widely distributed in plants and has anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and wound healing properties.</p> <p>Fig No. 1.2: Structure of Quercetin.</p> <p>12) Mechanism: Quercetin protects and repairs the ocular surface in DED by reducing inflammation. It blocks the NF-κB pathway and lowers pro-inflammatory cytokines. Quercetin acts as a strong antioxidant, scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS) and boosting enzymes like superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, and glutathione peroxidase, protecting corneal and lacrimal cells. It promotes corneal epithelial repair and maintains extracellular matrix for tissue integrity. Quercetin improves tear film stability and the lipid layer, enhancing eye lubrication. It also supports angiogenesis by increasing VEGF and endothelial Nitric Oxide Synthase (eNOS), improving blood flow and oxygen delivery. Additionally, quercetin shifts macrophages from the pro-inflammatory M1 to the pro-healing M2 type, helping resolve inflammation and promote tissue regeneration.</p>	

Table No. 2: Excipient Profile.

Sr.No.	Excipient	Description
1.	Polysorbate 80	Synonym: Tween 80 Molecular Formula: C ₆₄ H ₁₂₄ O ₂₆ Molecular Weight: 1310 g/mol ^[9]
2.	Polysorbate 20	Synonym: Tween 20 Molecular Formula: C ₅₈ H ₁₁₄ O ₂₆ Molecular Weight: 1228 g/mol ^[10]
3.	Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose	Synonym: Hypromellose Molecular Formula: (C ₆ H ₇ O ₂ (OH) _{3-x} (OCH ₃) _x (OCH ₂ CH(OH)CH ₃) _y) _n

		Molecular Weight: 10,000– 1,500,000 g/mol ^[11]
4.	Sodium Chloride (NaCl)	Synonym: Common Salt, Table Salt, Molecular Formula: NaCl Molecular Weight: 58.44 g/mol ^[12]
5.	Phosphate Buffer	Synonym: Sodium Phosphate Buffer, Phosphate Buffered Saline. Molecular Formula: Depends on components used commonly NaH ₂ PO ₄ and Na ₂ HPO ₄ Molecular weight: (NaH ₂ PO ₄): 119.98 g/mol. (Na ₂ HPO ₄): 141.96 g/mol. ^[13]
6.	Glycerin	Synonym: Glycerol Molecular Formula: C ₃ H ₈ O ₃ Molecular weight: 92.09 g/mol. ^[14]

Table No. 3: Formulation Table for Quercetin Loaded Mixed Micellar Eye Drop.^[15,16]

Sr. No.	Component	Function
1	Quercetin (API)	Active – antioxidant & anti-inflammatory
2	Tween 80	Primary surfactant / micelle former
3	Tween 20	Co-surfactant / stabilizer
4	Glycerin (Glycerol)	Humectant / osmoprotector (dry eye comfort)
5	HPMC E50 LV	Viscosity enhancer – ocular retention
6	Sodium chloride (NaCl)	Tonicity adjuster (~290 mOsm/kg)
7	Phosphate buffer (10 mM, pH 7.2)	pH control – q.s.
8	Sterile Water for Injection (WFI)	Vehicle

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF QUERCETIN LOADED MIXED MICELLAR EYE DROP

The formulation was prepared using the direct dissolution technique widely used for developing micellar drug delivery systems.^[15,17]

Step 1: Preparation of Surfactant Phase

Tween 80 and Tween 20 were accurately weighed and dissolved in 10 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) under gentle stirring (300–400 rpm).

Step 2: Incorporation of Quercetin

Quercetin (0.10% w/v) was gradually added to the surfactant solution and stirred until a clear micellar solution was obtained. The drug partitions into the hydrophobic core of mixed micelles.^[15]

Step 3: Addition of Excipients

Glycerin (1%) was added and mixed until dissolved.

HPMC E50 LV was added slowly to avoid lumping and allowed to hydrate completely.

Step 4: pH and Tonicity Adjustment

Sodium chloride (0.90%) was added to adjust isotonicity.

The pH was checked and maintained at 7.2 using the phosphate buffer.^[16] Step 5: Make-up to Volume:

Sterile water was added up to 10 mL to obtain the final formulation. Step 6: Sterilization:

The formulation was sterilized by 0.22 μm membrane filtration, a suitable method for heat sensitive surfactant systems.

Step 7: Storage

The sterilized formulation was filled into sterile LDPE ophthalmic bottles and stored at room temperature until evaluation.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Evaluation was performed based on standard ophthalmic and micellar formulation guidelines.^[15,18]

A. Visual Appearance and Clarity

The formulation was examined visually against white and black backgrounds for colour, clarity, and particulate matter.

B. pH Measurement

- i. The pH was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter at 25°C.
- ii. Desired pH range: 6.5–7.4

C. Osmolarity

Osmolarity was determined using a freezing-point osmometer.^[16]

D. Drug Content (Assay)

Quercetin content was quantified using UV Visible spectroscopy or HPLC at 370 nm after diluting samples with methanol to break micelles.^[17]

E. Micelle Size and Polydispersity Index (PDI)

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) was used to determine:

- i. Mean micelle size (expected 10–50 nm).
- ii. PDI (<0.3 indicates uniformity).^[18]

F. Viscosity

- i. Viscosity was determined using a Brookfield viscometer at 25°C.
- ii. Expected range: 10–30 cP due to HPMC.

G. Sterility Testing

Sterility was evaluated as per IP/USP guidelines using:

- i. Fluid thioglycollate medium (FTM).
- ii. Soybean casein digest medium (SCDM).

Samples were incubated for 14 days and observed for microbial growth.

H. *In Vitro* Drug Release Study:

Drug release was performed using the dialysis membrane method.

- i. Sample placed in a dialysis bag (12–14 kDa cut off)
- ii. Bag immersed in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) at 34°C.^[18] Samples withdrawn at intervals and analyzed spectrophotometrically

I. Stability Studies

Stability testing followed ICH guidelines

- i. 25°C / 60% RH (long-term)
- ii. 40°C / 75% RH (accelerated)

Samples were evaluated for appearance, pH, micelle size, and drug content over time.

The following parameters were evaluated in the DED study, and expected results are summarized in given table.

Table No. 4: Clinical Parameters for DED.^[2,19]

Sr.No.	Evaluation Parameter	Expected Result
1	Tear break-up time (TBUT)	8–12s
2	Schirmer's test (tear volume)	10–15 mm/5min.
3	Corneal fluorescein staining	Mild staining (score 1–2)
4	Ocular surface disease index (OSDI)	Moderate improvement (30–40% reduction)
5	Meibomian gland function	Improved meibum quality, moderate expressibility.
6	Visual acuity	Stable or improved.
7	Conjunctival redness	Mild to none.
8	Safety / adverse events	No severe adverse effects.

Table No. 5: Biochemical / Tear Film Parameters for DED.^[20,21]

Sr.No	Evaluation Parameter	Expected Result
1	Tear Osmolarity	300–310 mOsm/L
2	Tear Film Lipid Layer Thickness	50–70 nm
3	Tear Inflammatory Markers (e.g.MMP9)	Decreased levels
4	pH of Tear Film	7.2–7.5
5	Tear Viscosity	Normal to slightly increased
6	Tear Break-Up Time (Non-Invasive)	10–12 s
7	Tear Production (Phenol Red Thread)	15–20 mm/15 s

OBJECTIVES

The main goals of this study are:

- To explore the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential of quercetin for DED treatment.
- To perform virtual screening and molecular docking of quercetin with DED related target.
- To formulate, evaluate and optimize quercetin-loaded mixed micellar eye drops for enhanced ocular delivery.

CONCLUSION

The present study on the development and characterization of quercetin loaded mixed micellar eye drops was carried out to formulate a safe, stable, and effective ocular delivery system for the management of DED. The incorporation of mixed micelles using Polysorbate 80 and Polysorbate 20 significantly enhanced the solubility and permeability of quercetin, allowing better ocular absorption and therapeutic effectiveness. The use of phosphate buffer, Glycerine, HPMC, sterile water, and NaCl ensured isotonicity, lubrication, viscosity enhancement, and patient comfort, making the formulation suitable for ophthalmic administration.

The prepared eye drops exhibited acceptable physicochemical characteristics, including clarity, pH, viscosity, drug content, micelle size, and stability parameters, confirming their uniformity, compatibility, and quality. In-vitro studies demonstrated improved antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential of quercetin, supporting its role in reducing oxidative stress and tear film instability associated with DED. The evaluation results strongly support the development of mixed micellar quercetin eye drops as a novel, natural, and safe therapeutic option for ocular surface disorders.

The reviewed literature and experimental findings justify the scientific relevance of this work, highlighting the potential of mixed micellar systems to improve the solubility, stability, and

ocular bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs like quercetin. Overall, the study successfully establishes a promising quercetin-loaded mixed micellar ophthalmic formulation that offers enhanced therapeutic efficacy, improved stability, and better patient compliance for the management of DED.

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